

DESIGN AND CONSTRUCTION OF AUTOMATED PRECISION COIL WINDER AIDED WITH COMPUTER INTERPHASEOMOROGIUWA ESEOSA¹ UHUNMWANGHO ROLAND²

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This work is on design and construction of automated precision coil winder aided with computer inter phase. The essence is to overcome the challenges inherent in analogue winding machines such as over winding, misalignment, non-uniform windings, inaccuracy and slowness in windings among others. The design is an electromechanical system (consist of both electric and mechanical section) and were analyzed accordingly. Performance assessment was then carried out and found the machine to be satisfactory in overcoming these peculiar challenges of analogue machines

INTRODUCTION

Coils are used practically for all kinds of electrical applications such as transformers, relays, motors, generators, inductors, solenoids, fans, etc. Originally, coils were wound by hand, thus only few coils could be produced at a time and subsequently had lots of winding problems of different kinds. As demand increases the need to wound coils in large quantity, with improved quality, hence the need for automation (J.C. Darley, 1998) arises. Gradually, coil winding machines were invented beginning with manual (hand-crank operated) winding machine to the current coil winding machines with mechanical counters that are still currently been improved upon through modern innovations. Winding coils manually usually results in some problems such as; over-winding or overshoot and non-uniformity of wires across each pole (Penrose H.W, 1999), thus reducing the quality of the wound coil, because electromechanical properties of electric coil depends on turns ratio of coil, and the uniformity of the outlay of the wires for stable uniform magnetic flux. The technology involved in coil windings in terms of gauge accuracy and speed to meet the ever increasing demand for these electrical appliances is still a challenge. This paper aim to design and construct automatic digital coil winder prototype as an alternative to manual/hand winding and analogue winders. This will be achieved by applying embedded microprocessor control technology, precision stepping and computer software-based control to produce and a highly-accurate automatic machine. This design is limited to winding medium or small gauges of range between 20-40 ASWG (American Standard Wire Gauge). The work also tried to correct manual coil winding defects such as disarrangement, misalignment and non-uniformity of the windings per pole that often tend to lower reliability and reduced performance of electrical appliances/devices (J. Allen and others, 2003).

LITERATURE REVIEW

Their variety of applications and widespread use has made coil winding an important process to produce quality coils to meet consumer demands. As a result, coil winding techniques and machine prototypes have been designed over the years to eliminate problems associated with older models and to keep up with technological advances, incorporating new innovations to create better, faster, cheaper, safer, more versatile and superior models. Some previous designs and techniques include the work by J.R. Langham 1948, H.D Woodward 1960, C.Ronald *et al* 1999, T.Gary 2005 among others. J.R. Langham's work in 1948 presented classic hand-winding techniques used for coil winding. Despite using Lathe machine and mechanical counter, the researcher admitted that the final wound coils had faults and there were several overlaps in the turns. Langham then gave about 7 tips to wound a neat coil to improve the systems/appliance efficiency. H.D Woodward's own design in 1960 incorporated analog automation to solve the deficiencies resulting from the hand-winding or manual winding techniques previously used. His model was based on a single DC motor, to which a spindle was attached and held on bearings. The coil former (core) on which the coil is to be wound is placed on the spindle and secured in place by cone brackets. The transverse drive, which guides the wire being wound horizontally, to ensure they are neatly arranged on the coil, was fabricated

using brass with two rollers to guide the wires, attached to it. While this design innovatively eliminates the problem of overlapping windings and produced more consistent layers, the problem of over wind and human errors still remains. R Casser *et al* in 1999 designed and constructed Coil winding machine. The prototype design of R Casser *et al* is an improved version of the work of H.D Woodward, though both systems are analog automation models. However, a few additional features make their design superior to that of Woodward. Fast or slow wound is possible though same problems of overshoot/over wound still persist and if the transverse is misaligned for any reason, it leads to series of overlapping windings for each turn and the coil will have to be driven back and forward again and again. T Gary in 2005 designed and constructed coil winder and the mechanical counter used for analog model by previous researchers was replaced with two 7 stage ripple counters. The limitation to this design is that it has foot pedal which means it is directly controlled by human operators hence affecting the quality of final wound coil (human error). L.Robert in 2009 designed and constructed computer controlled high stepping automatic coil winder with limitation of not been able to alter the already written program. F. Jorg and D Andreas in 2012 designed and constructed Robot-Based Winding-Process for Flexible Coil Production. These researchers introduced robotics technology to the field of coil winding and based their method on industrial delta-robot which places the wire on a programmable trajectory. The winding movement is generated solely by moving the wire guide on a bobbin-adapted trajectory. This approach offers several advantages particularly as the winding motion can easily be adapted to the requirements of different winding products and made it possible to wind virtually any winding pattern on arbitrary formed cores without special wire guides. For example, some electronic products require windings to be integrated into the circuit board or housing. Such “integrated windings” can easily be made using this method (J. Franke and A. Dodbroschke, 2012). The short coming of this approach is that programming the free-trajectory tripod robot is not easy for general users as it requires some skilled knowledge. Furthermore, this machine is adapted mainly for winding customized coils (J. Franke and A. Dodbroschke, 2012). The winding speed is slower here and hence it cannot do volume (bulk) work quickly.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The automatic coil winder is an electromechanical system hence both the electrical and mechanical design is considered. This design is implemented using Direct Current (DC) stepper motors for precision stepping, microcontroller for enhanced control preset inputs, liquid crystal display (LCD) to readout /display the status of the winding process at any instant, Universal Serial Bus (USB), software from which it can be controlled, power rectification unit, supply circuits and motor control circuits. DC stepper motor is used because of its ability to rotate precise angle in response to a particular input. The motor is controlled using Darlington transistor based motor drive integrated circuit. The microcontroller receives the inputs (required no of turns) from the preset input keypad or a PC through the USB port and then processes the input and control the motor via the motor control circuit. The output is displayed through the LCD. Feedback to the microprocessor is configured using turn counter made as “slotted switch” to give one input per revolution of the motor & coil spindle. Figure 1.0 shows control block diagram depicting the design methodology.

Figure 1.0: Simple Control Block Diagram Depicting the Design Methodology

Power Supply: The power supply unit consists of step-down transformer, rectification unit, filtering and voltage stabilization circuit. It receives input of 220V AC rms and supply voltages of 12V and 5V DC for the stepper motor and the microcontroller respectively. Power supply circuit is shown in figure 2.0.

Figure 2.0: Power Supply Circuit

The transformer receives 220V supply at the primary, from the mains and produce 12V AC output at the secondary. The secondary terminals are then connected to a full wave bridge rectifier to produce 12V DC output. Thus the full wave bridge rectifier gives a rectified 12V DC output. This is then applied to the electrolytic filter capacitor connected in parallel to give 12V DC ripple voltage required by the stepper motor. For the microcontroller 5V DC stabilized voltage is required. This is obtained using 7805 voltage regulator IC, which converts the 12V DC ripple voltage to a stabilized 5V DC voltage for the micro controller. Thus the power supply block produces 5V DC regulated voltage applied to the microcontroller and a 12V DC voltage applied to the motor drive circuit.

Microcontroller: The microcontroller used is AT89S52 because of its low-power, high-performance CMOS 8-bit microcontroller with 8K bytes programmable Flash memory and it is designed with static logic for operation down to zero frequency and supports two software selectable power saving modes. The Idle Mode stops the CPU while allowing the RAM, timer/counters, serial port, and interrupt system to continue functioning. The Power-down mode saves the RAM contents but freezes the oscillator, disabling all other chip functions until the next interrupt or hardware reset. The idle mode is used for this work to allow the RAM to receive inputs while the machine is idle, so that the machine will drain its stored power and have to be reset every time it is left idle for a while. It consists of 32 single byte (8-bit) registers, accumulator (Acc), two temporary registers TMP2 & TMP1, flag register – PSW (Program Status Word), stack pointer, instruction register, program counter, memory address register, interrupt address register, timing and control unit and linked to both the RAM address register, and internal flash memory. The 32 input/output lines form 4 ports (8-bit each) – port 0, 1, 2, 3 & 4 through which it can receive inputs and instructions and produce outputs. The timing signal is generated externally by a suitable crystal oscillator within the range of 1 – 22MHz. The more the speed required, the more the current consumption. For this work, balance speed and current consumption is chosen at 11.0592MHz. This timing signal along with the various control signals will be applied to the timing and control register. The AT89S52 microcontroller is used as the main control element. It will receive inputs from the keypad and PC, drive the stepper motor and output to the LED display.

Motor drive circuit: The motor drive circuit is based on ULN2003A IC package. It is a high voltage/ high current Darlington array, each containing 7 open collector Darlington pair's with common emitters,

integrated on a single chip (STMicroelectronics, 2002). Figure 3.0 is the Diagram Showing Each Driver (Grounding Omitted) [ST Microelectronics, 2002]

Each channel is rated at 500mA and can withstand peak currents of 600mA. Suppression diodes are included for inductive load driving and the inputs are pinned opposite the outputs to simplify the board layouts. This ULN2003A version is a 5V package that can interface to the TTL, CMOS logic families and the micro controller unit. So it is compatible with the motor drive IC. The ULN2003A is powered by 12V DC, which it supplies to the motor. It has 16 pins. Each pin on the left side is the input pin with its corresponding output pin opposite to it, i.e. IN 1→OUT 16, IN2→OUT 15 etc. Pin 9 is point of application of the 12VDC power and pin 8 is the ground (GND). When a high pulse (+5V = logical 1) is supplied to pin 1, its output pin (16)–is connected to ground, causing the power supply of 12V DC to flow through it to the particular stepper motor terminal it is connected to, and the motor rotates through one step angle. Similarly, applying a high pulse to pin 2 causes 12V DC to flow through pin 15 to the next motor terminal producing further rotation through another precise step angle. Applying a high pulse to pin 3 causes 12V DC to flow through pin 4 and so on till pin 7. This way, the IC can drive the stepper motor through as many precise rotations as desired, depending on the number of applied pulses. These high/low pulses are achieved through the programmed microcontroller AT89S52.

Stepper Motors: Stepper motor is a form of synchronous motor, which rotates at precise angular distance (called step) for each pulse that is delivered to its drive circuit. (J. B. Gupta, 2011). Because the step pulses can be counted digitally and stopped when the desired number have been delivered, stepper motors lend themselves to digital control by a programmable controller or on-line computer. These motors can also provide precise open-loop speed control, since their rotational speed is determined solely by the step pulse frequency, independent of load (J. B. Gupta, 2011). DC unipolar stepper motors of the variable reluctance are used for this work. The motors both have step angles of 7.5° (i.e each energizing of its coil should rotate the shaft 7.5°). This means the number of pulses required to wind a given number of turns can be obtained directly. Say 20 turns is required to be wound; $1 \text{ turn} = 360^\circ$; $20 \text{ turns} = 360^\circ \times 20 = 7200^\circ \therefore$

$no. of pulses = \frac{7200^{\circ}}{7.5^{\circ}} = 960 pulses$. Therefore sending 960 pulses to the stepper motor through the motor drive IC will cause it to wind 20 turns with precision. This is the basic principle of operation of the automatic coil winder. The microcontroller would calculate the number of pulses using the formula;

$$no. of pulses = \frac{no. of turns \times 360^{\circ}}{step angle}$$

Programmed into it, generate the required number of pulses and apply it to the stepper motor through the motor drive IC.

LCD Output Display: The LCD employed to display the output number of turns and other readings is the LCD – 016MOO2B by Vishay and it is a 16×2 character LCD. Pin 1 (Vss) for ground, & +5V power is supplied through pin 2 (Vdd). Pin 3 is for contrast adjustment through which the dark or light contrast may be adjusted i.e. the display intensity may be made darker or lighter. Pin 4 (RS) is used to send commands/data – Commands when activated high and data when activated low. Commands include: shift position, register select, etc. Pin 5 (R/W) is the read/write pin – read when activated high and write when activated low. Pin 6 (E) is the enable pin to toggle between a high and low state, i.e. H→L & L←H. Pin 7 – 14 (DB₀ – DB₇) form the main data bus line and can also be active high or active low. Pin 15 & 16 (A/Vee and K) form the power supply for the back lighting provided using +4.2V LED to provide the extra lighting required to view the contents of the LCD display.

Keypad: The keypad used for the automatic coil winder is a generic 4×4 input keypad formed from an array of push button switches. When awaiting an input, the microcontroller continuously scans all the 4 rows (row A,B,C & D) in turn with a +5V DC input and checks each of the 4 columns (column 1,2,3 & 4) simultaneously for an output. If say key 8 is depressed, a +5V output will occur at column 4 from row D, which corresponds to 08D (8 – decimal) to the microcontroller. If say key 9 is depressed, a +5V output will occur at column 1 from row C, which corresponds to 09D (9 – decimal) to the microcontroller. This way any number of inputs can be sent to the microcontroller. Keys A –F may also be configured for special functions and commands.

RS232 Logic Level Converter: The microcontroller functions using two logic levels; +5V for high and 0V for low. Most computers however are designed to function using logic levels of the range of +3 to +12 (high) and -3 to -12 (low). For example, a typical HP laptop/system uses +7 & -7 for its high and low voltage levels. For this reason, there cannot be direct communication between a PC and the microcontroller. In order to facilitate communication between a PC and the device microcontroller, a logic level converter is used. The RS232 logic level converter acts as an interface between the PC and the microcontroller. It converts the logic state of the PC to the logic level of the microcontroller and vice versa, while maintaining the information being transmitted.

MECHANICAL DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The first motor is attached to a spindle, on which the core is to be wound is mounted on. Shackles are present on the spindle to fasten and secure the core. The second motor is attached to a threaded spindle. On this spindle is placed wire guide using threaded rollers. The microcontroller generates the appropriate pulses to drive the winding motor. As the winding motor rotates, the wire is wound around the core. figure 4.0 shows the mechanical design diagram used for the study.

Figure 4.0 Depiction of Mechanical Design Methodology

TESTS, RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, tests were carried out on various components used in constructing the automatic coil winder. These tests include both static and dynamic tests to determine their respective reliabilities, before hardware implementation. The completed coil winding machine is put through tests and performance evaluations to prove its functionality and reliability.

Components Tests

The major components used for this design are: microcontroller, two motor drive ICs, LCD, RS232/MAX232 logic level converter, input keypad, power supply module and two stepper motors. Others include; resistors, electrolytic capacitors, diodes, a transformer, crystal oscillator, bridge rectifier (full-wave), voltage regulator.

Hardware Implementation

For the frame, wood is used because of it allows for easy modification. It is used for both the sides and bottom of the winder have a 1/2 inch nominal thickness. The sides are cut to 8" X 8", and the bottom is 8" X 18" whose supports are 3/4" X 2 1/2" X 8", and the channels cut into the supports are 3/8" deep. Both sides are set up in the channels cut into the supports. Screws are used at first to allow for later modification. A drawing depicting the measurements and placements is given in figure 6.0

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Figure 6.0 Technical Description of Frame

This base is cut to attach a nut which will guide it on the threaded spindle. A short tube is also attached to it for the other rod to balance the transverse as shown in figure 7.0

Figure 7.0: Base for Transverse

The motors are mounted on the frame and the spindles are inserted into their respective holes as shown in figure 8.0. Motors and Spindle Mounted on Frame are shown in figure 9.0

Figure 8.0: Motors and Spindle Mounted on Frame

The electrical circuits are built using a Vero board. The board and its components are shown in figure 9.0 before it is mounted on the frame.

Figure 9.0: Assembled Electrical Circuit

CONCLUSION

This work has presented the design and construction of an automatic coil winder. Stepper motors was used for precision positioning to avoid over wound problems. The stepper motor was controlled digitally using programmable microprocessor. Most of the commercially available coil winders, being analog based requires some form of human supervisory control. This design is digital based and incorporates programmable microprocessor thus enabling it to operate automatically. An electronic LCD display was used in place of mechanical counter to display the current number of turns and eliminated eliminate deadlock problems often associated with mechanical counters due to friction at high speeds. Additional control through computer's USB (upgrade from parallel ports) interface was also included to increase its versatility and enable the winder to be programmed and controlled using computer software (in this work visual basic program was written) to automatically estimate the wire length and stop the winding process when the required number of windings are reached.

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